

Protocol for developing a minimum set of core parameters and outcomes to be measured when assessing the microbiome in FMT trials

Version 2.1, (June 02, 2023)

Investigators responsible for the research:

- **Isabelle Boutron:** (1) Université Paris Cité and Université Sorbonne Paris Nord, Inserm, INRAE, Center for Research in Epidemiology and Statistics (CRESS), F-75004 Paris, France; (2) Centre d'Epidémiologie Clinique, AP-HP, Hôpital Hôtel Dieu, Paris, France. isabelle.boutron@aphp.fr
- **Alexander Jarde:** (1) Université Paris Cité and Université Sorbonne Paris Nord, Inserm, INRAE, Center for Research in Epidemiology and Statistics (CRESS), F-75004 Paris, France; (2) Centre d'Epidémiologie Clinique, AP-HP, Hôpital Hôtel Dieu, Paris, France. alexander.jarde@cochrane.fr

Co-investigators:

- **Emmanuelle Maguin:** MICALIS, INRA, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, Jouy-en-Josas, France
- **Aicha Kriaa:** MICALIS, INRA, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, Jouy-en-Josas, France

Table of contents

Protocol for developing a minimum set of core parameters and outcomes to be measured when assessing the microbiome in FMT trials.....	1
Table of contents.....	2
Summary.....	3
Introduction.....	4
Background and objectives.....	4
Methods.....	4
Stakeholders.....	4
Information sources and preparation of the Delphi questionnaire.....	4
Steering committee.....	5
Consensus process.....	5
Analysis of missing data.....	6
Ethics and dissemination.....	8
Timeline.....	8
Funding.....	8
Conflicts of interest.....	8
Appendices.....	8
Appendix 1 : Outline of the initial survey (Round 1).....	9
Appendix 2 : Invitation letter and reminder email.....	19
Invitation letter:.....	19
Reminder email:.....	21

Summary

Introduction: Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) has shown promising microbiome-altering results and has been proposed in clinical practice to treat certain diseases. However, there is heterogeneity in the definitions, the technological and analytical methods and the thresholds used as markers of the effectiveness of the intervention and even their relevance is discussed.

Objective: The purpose of this study is to identify a minimum set of core parameters and outcomes to be measured when assessing the microbiome in FMT trials, regardless of the disease or condition being treated.

Methods: A first list of outcomes was obtained by mapping FMT-related outcomes reported in FMT trials registered in several international registries. Based on this list, a first draft of the survey was created and a diverse pool of professionals and experts were invited to provide feedback and comments during an online workshop. The resulting final version represents the first round of a Delphi survey. A variety of stakeholders involved in the development and evaluation of FMT interventions will be invited to answer the survey with the aim of reaching consensus, over two or three rounds, on what outcomes should be systematically measured in FMT trials and how they should be measured. Participants will be asked to rate their perceived importance of each outcome using a 6-point Likert scale. For those outcomes considered important, they will also be asked about how to measure them and the feasibility of all trials doing so. For the second round we will provide feedback in form of descriptive statistics (plots) for each item, which is expected to lead to a greater consensus. A third round will be done only if necessary.

Analyses: Items where $\geq 80\%$ participants score 1-3 will be considered unimportant, while items where $\geq 80\%$ of participants score them 5-6 will be considered important. Among those outcomes for which there is consensus regarding their importance, those that are also considered feasible by $\geq 80\%$ of respondents will be included in the final list of outcomes. At the end of the process, this final list of included outcomes will be shared with all Delphi participants (who completed at least one round) to allow for final feedback. We will analyse the potential for attrition bias.

Introduction

Background and objectives

Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) is a promising therapy for chronic diseases associated with gut microbiota alterations. While healthcare communities have been assessing FMT with renewed interest, technical and logistical challenges still loom in bringing standardized interventions into clinical practice. Heterogeneity in measured outcomes across trials is increasingly known to impact the ability to compare findings and could potentially imply little significance to healthcare professionals and patients. Reaching a consensus on the minimum set of core parameters and outcomes to be measured when assessing the microbiome in FMT trials is needed to ensure that meaningful endpoints for all stakeholders are being captured and reported, and further improve the relevance of the trial's findings.

The aim of this study is to identify this minimum set of core parameters and outcomes to be measured when assessing the microbiome in FMT trials, regardless of the disease or condition being treated.

Methods

Stakeholders

We aim to recruit a diverse pool of professionals and participants involved in the development and assessment of FMT interventions, including researchers, health professionals, industry representatives, etc. We will identify researchers by searching for authors with at least 10 publications in the last 10 years related to FMT using the Web of Science's author ranking when searching for 'Fecal microbiota transplantation'. Clinicians experienced in using FMT in trials and industry representatives will be recruited by snowball sampling using the Human Microbiome Action collaborative platform.

Information sources and preparation of the Delphi questionnaire

We did a systematic review of trial registries with FMT as (at least) one of the intervention arms and with a planned start date between 2017 and 2022. Outcomes related to FMT were extracted and mapped, advised by content experts.

Once we finalised the initial list of outcomes (and their measurement methods) based on the results of the systematic review we organised a two-days-long online workshop (12 and 13 December 2022) in which we invited a variety of stakeholders to comment and expand on this initial list. They also provided feedback on the first draft of the survey to be used during the first round of the Delphi survey, including the scoring system, item structure, response options, wording, etc. Based on this feedback, and on additional comments from members of the Human Microbiome Action collaborative platform, a final version of the survey was prepared.

Steering committee

A steering committee, consisting of at least two members with methodological expertise (IB, AJ) and two members with clinical expertise (EM, AK), will be established to make the necessary decisions throughout the processing of the results.

Consensus process

Stakeholders will be invited to participate in a two-stage Delphi survey to reach consensus on the importance, feasibility and measurement methods of each of the listed outcomes (Figure 1). The survey will be online to allow for a large number of participants regardless of where they are based. It is expected that most of the stakeholders will be comfortable with the survey being in English, which was therefore not translated to any other language.

An outline of the survey is presented in Appendix 1 and it will be implemented through a specialised medical research company (KPL Paris). The platform used to set up the questionnaire, manage the individual invitations to participate and collect the individual answers to the questionnaire is ClinInfo. This platform is compliant with RGPD rules and will provide the results from the questionnaires anonymously.

Each potential participant identified will be sent an email invite, with up to two reminder emails (Appendix 2). For each round, participants will have 3 weeks to answer the survey, with reminders being sent at the beginning of the second and third week.

In the first Delphi round we will explain the scope and goals of the process in layman terms. Participants will be asked to rate their perceived importance of each outcome using a 6-point Likert scale. An 'unable to score' option will be available as well for participants who lack the technical or clinical expertise to assess a particular outcome. In addition, participants in the first round will have the possibility of suggesting additional outcomes that they consider critical.

For each outcome, a series of follow-up questions will be asked if the participant scored it as 3 or more. These questions refer to how the outcome ought to be measured and the feasibility for all trials to do so.

Once the response period is over, items where $\geq 80\%$ participants scored 1-3 will be considered unimportant and excluded from the next round. If $\geq 80\%$ of participants scored an item 5-6, it will be considered important and will not be included in the next round (Table 1). Items receiving any other scores, as well as any additional outcomes suggested by at least two participants during round 1, will be included in the next Delphi round (Figure 1). Any modifications to the wording of the items, based on respondents' comments, will be considered by the steering committee.

Regarding the measurement instruments for each outcome, only those being selected by $\geq 50\%$ of the respondents will be included in the next Delphi round, as well as any new instruments suggested by at least two participants.

Table 1: Decision rules

Time point	Condition	Interpretation	Effect
After Rounds 1 & 2	≥ 80% of responses 5, 6	Consensus in favour	Remove from Round 2 and keep for final assessment
After Rounds 1 & 2	≥ 80% of responses 1, 2, or 3	Consensus against	Remove from Round 2
After Round 2	≥ 80% of responses 5, 6 for importance & ≥ 80% of responses 5, 6 for feasibility	Important and feasible outcome	Include in final list

In the second Delphi round we will provide a summary of the results from the previous round (keeping individual answers anonymous to avoid responses being influenced by particular individuals). This summary will consist of a list of outcomes for which consensus had been met (for inclusion and for exclusion) and, for each of the remaining outcomes, a frequency plot. In addition, participants will have access to the responses they gave in round one, which will enable them to consider different opinions and modify their original answers. It is expected that this will lead to a convergence of the responses towards a consensus.

After the response period is over, outcomes will be classified as important, unimportant, or uncertain following the same criteria as in round 1 (Table 1). Any remaining outcomes for which consensus is not achieved will be discussed by the authors to decide, based on the ratings received, if they should be included (the default being the exclusion of important, but not critical outcomes). The reasons for including any of these items will be documented and reported.

A third Delphi round will be considered if the steering committee considers it necessary to reach consensus on those items for which there remains no consensus after round 2.

A final list of outcomes will be compiled including all outcomes that were considered both important (≥80% of responses 5 or 6) and feasible to measure (≥80% of responses 5 or 6). At the end of the process, the final list of included outcomes will be shared with all Delphi participants (who answered to at least one round) to allow for any final comments (Figure 1).

Analysis of missing data

We will analyse the potential for attrition bias 1) by comparing the responses of those participants who do not respond two subsequent rounds with those who did; and 2) by comparing the number of drop-outs between the different stakeholder groups.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the consensus (Delphi) process

Ethics and dissemination

Ethical approval: After consultation with Inserm's Ethics Evaluation Committee (CEEI/IRB), we were informed that no ethics approval was required for this survey.

Informed consent: All participants will receive an email invitation email explaining the purpose of the study, including a link to the website of the survey. A pop-up screen will appear upon clicking on the questionnaire. This screen will inform the participant that their data will be stored for the purpose of the study (data collected: email address and data provided into the survey). The participant must accept before entering the survey.

Confidentiality and data protection: the survey will be implemented through a specialised medical research company (KPL Paris). The platform used to set up the questionnaire, manage the individual invitations to participate and collect the individual answers to the questionnaire is ClinInfo. This platform is compliant with RGPD rules and will provide the results from the questionnaires anonymously.

Dissemination: In addition to sharing the final list of outcomes with the study participants, we will also share with them the pre-print version of the manuscript. We aim to disseminate the results of the survey through peer-reviewed and open access publication.

Timeline

	2023								
Month	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Piloting of survey, revise questions if needed									
Round 1									
Analyses of round 1 and preparation of round 2									
Round 2									
Analyses of round 2									
Report									

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964590. The funders have no role in the study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscripts.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

Appendices

- Appendix 1: Outline of the initial survey (Round 1)
- Appendix 2: Invitation letter and reminder email

Appendix 1 : Outline of the initial survey (Round 1)

Introduction

Thank you for your interest in contributing to this project...

Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) is a promising therapy for chronic diseases associated with gut microbiota alterations. While healthcare communities have been assessing FMT with renewed interest, technical and logistical challenges still loom in bringing standardized interventions into clinical practice. Heterogeneity in measured outcomes across trials is increasingly known to impact the ability to compare findings and could potentially imply little significance to healthcare professionals and patients. Reaching a consensus on the minimum set of core parameters and outcomes to be measured when assessing the microbiome in FMT trials is needed to ensure that meaningful endpoints for all stakeholders are being captured and reported, and further improve the relevance of the trial's findings.

A common method for reaching a consensus on what outcomes to include in such a set of outcomes is called a Delphi survey, in which 1) experts are asked to give their opinion on what outcomes are most important, 2) statements are reformulated and the results are summarized and sent back to the experts, who are then 3) asked again to rate the importance of the outcomes. In the framework of the International Human Microbiome Coordination and Support Action (IHMCSA), we planned a maximum of up to three such rounds to reach a consensus.

This initial list of outcomes in the current survey was elaborated based on a systematic review of registered FMT-related clinical trials, but you are encouraged to add any other outcome that you think we might have missed. Please note that this consultation can be filled in by individual experts from academics, industry, regulation/policy makers, physicians, healthcare professionals, and organizations.

Further details on this project can be found in our protocol, or you can email us directly (alexander.jarde@inserm.fr) to ask any other question you might have.

<p>In what stakeholder group(s) are you? Multiple responses are allowed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Researcher<input type="checkbox"/> Healthcare professional<input type="checkbox"/> Industry representative<input type="checkbox"/> Patient representative/patient<input type="checkbox"/> Member of the public/citizen<input type="checkbox"/> Policy maker<input type="checkbox"/> Regulatory expert<input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____
--	--

If they answered 'Health professional' above:

What is your specialty?

- Clostridium difficile* infection
- Other infectious diseases: _____
- Metabolic diseases
- Obesity
- Cardiovascular disease
- Diabetes
- Hepatic diseases
- Inflammatory bowel disease
- Irritable bowel syndrome
- Psychiatric disorders
- Neurodegenerative diseases
- Gerontology
- Pediatrics
- Other:

What to measure - measures of the microbiome

Please indicate how relevant you think each of these outcomes are in clinical trials assessing efficacy or effectiveness of FMT, independently of the disease to be treated. Our goal is to identify outcomes that would be **relevant** to collect in **all FMT trials analyzing the microbiota, regardless of the disease treated**, and that would allow researchers to compare and combine the different studies.

For each outcome, we will ask you to rate the relevance of the outcome on a scale from 1 to 6 (= little importance; 6 = critical importance), where higher values (5, 6) represent favorable responses and lower values (1 to 3) indicate negative responses. We encourage you to try to avoid the middle scores, though. If you feel you lack the expertise to rate a particular outcome, you can check the additional 'unable to score' option.

For each core outcome we will also ask you about *how* you think that outcome should be measured and the feasibility of doing it, including questions on:

- Concrete definitions / measures
- Time points at which they should be measured
- (if applicable) methods considered acceptable for this measurement

Do you think it is important to characterize fecal microbiota of the recipient in all FMT trials?

	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance	
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
Do you think it is important to characterize fecal microbiota of the recipient before the FMT intervention in all FMT trials?									
Do you think it is important to characterize fecal microbiota of the recipient after the intervention in all FMT trials?									

Feel free to explain your answer (free text box [max 100 words])

Do you think it is important to characterize fecal microbiota of the donor in all FMT trials?

	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance	
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
Do you think it is important to characterize fecal microbiota of the donor in all FMT trials?									

Feel free to explain your answer (free text box [max 100 words])

Regardless of the time points at which you measure the disease-related outcomes, at what point do you think it would be appropriate to characterize the recipient gut microbiome in all FMT trials?

	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Baseline (just before the FMT)								
Within 1 week after FMT								
1 to 3 weeks after FMT								
4 to 6 weeks after FMT								
6 months after FMT								
Other (please specify) _____								

Feel free to explain your answer (free text box [max 100 words])

When characterizing the composition of the gut microbiome, should we refer to:

- Bacteria
- Virus
- Fungi
- Others: _____

Should we assess the composition of the gut microbiome, or function, or microbiome metabolites?

	Unable to score	little importance				critical importance	
		1	2	3	4	5	6
How important is it to measure the microbiome <u>composition</u> in all FMT trials?							
How important is it to measure the microbiome <u>function</u> in all FMT trials?							

Alpha* diversity	Unable to score	little importance				critical importance	
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Should Alpha* diversity of microbiota be measured before the FMT intervention in all FMT trials? *: Popup text: Alpha diversity is a measure of microbiome diversity within a single sample/ecosystem (<i>i.e.</i> , within-sample diversity)							
Should Alpha* diversity of microbiota be measured after the FMT intervention in all FMT trials?							

*: Popup text: Alpha diversity is a measure of microbiome diversity within a single sample/ecosystem (<i>i.e.</i> , within-sample diversity)							
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)							

if they answered ≥ 3

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

How to measure alpha diversity?
Choose the index you think is best or suggest one that is not listed.

<input type="checkbox"/> Unable to score	<input type="checkbox"/> ACE* index *: Popup text: Abundance-based Coverage Estimator (ACE) reflects OTU abundances in a sample.	<input type="checkbox"/> Chao 1* index *: Popup text: Chao 1 index reflects OTU abundances while extrapolating to consider rare OTU that were not observed due to sampling.
<input type="checkbox"/> Shannon* diversity index *: Popup text: The Shannon index reflects the width of the OTU relative abundance distribution.	<input type="checkbox"/> Simpson's* index *: Popup text: The probability that two microorganisms randomly taken from the sample belong to the same OTU.	<input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____

Explain/comment your choice:

What methods would you consider as currently acceptable for this measurement? (multiple choices possible)

<input type="checkbox"/> Unable to score	<input type="checkbox"/> 16S rRNA gene sequencing*	<input type="checkbox"/> Shotgun metagenomic sequencing*
<input type="checkbox"/> Flow cytometry*		
<input type="checkbox"/> Other:		

Comments regarding this outcome:

Evenness	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Should Evenness* of microbiota be measured in all FMT trials? *: Popup text: Evenness describes relative differences in the abundance of various species in the community								
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)								

if they answered ≥ 3

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

How to measure evenness?
Choose the index you think is best or suggest one that is not listed.

<input type="checkbox"/> Unable to score	<input type="checkbox"/> Camargo's evenness* * Camargo's Index of Evenness is unaffected by	<input type="checkbox"/> Simpson's evenness* *Pop-up: For Simpson's measure of
--	--	---

	species richness and is simple to compute and is relatively little affected by the rare species in the sample.	heterogeneity, maximum diversity is obtained when all abundances are equal and is relatively unaffected by the rare species in the sample.
<input type="checkbox"/> Other:		
<i>What methods would you consider as currently acceptable for this measurement?</i>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Unable to score	<input type="checkbox"/> 16S rRNA gene sequencing*	<input type="checkbox"/> Shotgun metagenomic sequencing*
<input type="checkbox"/> Flow cytometry*		
Comments regarding this outcome:		

Beta diversity	Unable to score	little to critical importance					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Should Beta* diversity comparing <u>donor and recipient</u> microbiota be measured in all FMT trials? *: Popup text: Beta diversity measures are estimates of similarity or dissimilarity between sample/ecosystem (between samples).							
Should Beta* diversity comparing the recipient microbiota <u>before and after the FMT intervention</u> be measured in all FMT trials? *: Popup text: Beta diversity measures are estimates of similarity or dissimilarity between sample/ecosystem (between samples).							
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)							

<i>if they answered ≥ 3</i>		
<i>How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])</i>		
<i>How to measure beta diversity?</i> Choose the index you think is best or suggest one that is not listed.		
<input type="checkbox"/> Unable to score	<input type="checkbox"/> Bray-Curtis dissimilarity* analysis / Canberra distances *: Popup text: Bray-Curtis dissimilarity reflects the abundance of microbes that are shared between samples, and the number of microbes found in each.	<input type="checkbox"/> UniFrac/ weighted unifrac* *: Popup text: UniFrac considers the phylogenetic relationships between microbes found in the different samples. Weighted UniFrac follows the same logic as Unweighted UniFrac, but also takes the abundances of microbes into account.
<input type="checkbox"/> Other:		
<i>What methods would you consider as currently acceptable for this measurement?</i>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Unable to score	<input type="checkbox"/> 16S rRNA gene sequencing*	<input type="checkbox"/> Shotgun metagenomic sequencing*
<input type="checkbox"/> Flow cytometry*		
Comments regarding this outcome:		

Outcomes that target specific microbes/microbe groups (either beneficial or harmful)...

Abundance of specific microbes (either beneficial or harmful)	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Should Abundance of specific microbes be measured in all FMT trials?								
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)								

if they answered 3 or more

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

How to measure this outcome?

Relative abundance of specific microbes Absolute abundance of specific microbes Presence of specific microbes

What would be the most informative and applicable taxonomical rank for all FMT studies?

Phyla Family Genera Species Strain

What methods would you consider as currently acceptable for this measurement?

Unable to score 16S rRNA gene sequencing* Shotgun metagenomic sequencing*
 Flow cytometry* quantitative PCR

Other: _____

Comments regarding this outcome: _____

Engraftment of the donor's microbiome into the recipient	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Should Engraftment of the donor's microbiome into the recipient be measured in all FMT trials? Engraftment refers to the process of acceptance and growth of transplanted fecal bacteria.								
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)								

if they answered 3 or more

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

How would you measure engraftment? [max x words]

How to measure this outcome?

Beta diversity between donor and host microbiota Number of colonies per gram of feces Total bacteria (by quantitative PCR)

level of given metabolites Other: _____

What sequencing methods would you consider as currently acceptable for this measurement?

Unable to score 16S rRNA gene sequencing* Shotgun metagenomic sequencing*
 Flow cytometry*

Comments regarding this outcome: _____

Gut virome and bacteriophages	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Should the gut virome and bacteriophages be explored in all FMT trials?								
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)								

if they answered 3 or more

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

How should the gut virome and bacteriophages be analyzed?

Other:

Comments regarding this outcome:

Metabolites as an estimate of gut microbiome activity	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Should Metabolites be measured in all FMT trials as an estimate of gut microbiome activity								
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)								

if they answered 3 or more

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

What methods would you recommend?

Which metabolomic method would you consider currently acceptable for this measurement?

Is there specific metabolites that should be considered as CORE outcome?

Unable to score

Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs)

Other:

Comments regarding this outcome:

Measures of microbiome activity through enzymatic activities	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Should measures of microbiome activity through enzymatic activities be included in all FMT trials?								
Briefly explain your answer (free text box)								

if they answered 3 or more

How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])

Which activity would you recommend to measure?

Unable to score

Diamine oxidase (DAO)

Other:

Comments regarding this outcome: _____

Is there any other **important** direct or indirect measure of the microbiome that you think was missing? _____

Additional outcome	Unable to score	little importance						critical importance	
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
Should this outcome be included in all FMT trials?									
<i>How feasible is it to measure this outcome in all/most FMT trials? (scale from 1 [not feasible] to 6 [very feasible])</i>									
Which method would you consider currently acceptable for this measurement	_____								
Comments regarding this outcome: _____									

Before answering the question, please review the respective definitions of standards and Standard Operating Procedures below:

Pre-Analytical Standards (CEN/TS, ISO)	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)
CEN/TS or ISO standards for sample pre-analytics are official documents that specify requirements ('mandatory'; no deviation permitted; expressed as 'shall') and give recommendations ('non-mandatory'; possible suitable choices, expressed as 'should') for the pre-analytical workflow of certain specimen types.	SOPs are written documents containing step-by-step instructions for laboratory procedures specific to a certain laboratory that the laboratory staff needs to follow.
They are evidence-based, written and agreed on by experts on a European (CEN) or international (ISO) level. They provide the state-of-the-art for national and international regulation (e.g., IVDR) and are considered by regulators to reduce the risk for IVD developers and users. They are applicable to a wider range of user-groups and are vendor neutral (i.e., they do not refer to specific products).	They are generated, reviewed, and approved by a particular laboratory. The information an SOP contains is more detailed and specific for the laboratory and its equipment, chemicals, reagents and procedure (e.g., defines the centrifugation speeds, temperature and duration).
CEN/TS and ISO pre-analytics standards provide the basis for SOPs.	SOPs are part of a laboratory's quality management system and have to comply with requirements of standards.

CEN, European Committee for Standardization; ISO, International Standards Organization; SOP, Standard Operating Procedure; IVD, In-vitro diagnostics; IVDR, IVD regulation.

Are you using Standard Operating Procedures regarding the collection, storage, and pre-analytical and analytical methods in your lab/institution/biobank?

For example, the SOPS proposed by the International Health and Medical Services (<https://human-microbiome.org/index.php#SOPS>)

- **No**
 - Do you think that having SOPs would be useful? Yes/no
 - Would you follow SOPs even if they add constraints on your current protocol? Yes/ no
 - What would be the benefits of having SOPs compared to your current practice? brief explanation
- **Yes**
 - Which SOP are you using
 - developed within my lab/institution/biobank
 - open access SOP shared by other labs/institutions/biobanks and adapted within my lab/institution/biobank,
 - other?
 - comment on why

Are you aware of any international standard regarding collection, storage, pre-analytical and/or analytical methods of microbiome samples?

- **No**
- **Yes**

Which international standards are you aware of?

Are you aware of guidelines regarding the collection, storage and treatment of samples?

- **No**
- **Yes**
 - Which guidelines are you aware of?
 - brief comment on why

Appendix 2: Invitation letter and reminder email

Invitation letter:

Subject: DELPHI Survey – Human Microbiome Action – Core outcomes in FMT

Dear Colleague,

We are inviting you as an expert to provide your feedback on the delineation of a consensual view on a minimum set of outcomes for the effect of Fecal Microbiota Transplantation (FMT) on the microbiome, regardless of the condition treated.

The DELPHI survey 'Fecal Microbiota Transplantation trials: What is the minimum set of outcomes to measure when assessing the effect on the microbiome' is launched in the framework of the European program IHMCSA - Human Microbiome Action (<https://humanmicrobiomeaction.eu/>). It aims to achieve a consensus on:

- (i) a minimum set of outcomes for the effect of FMT on the microbiome, regardless of the condition treated
- (ii) how to measure each of the outcomes identified and the feasibility of them being measured in all/most future trials.

The survey is structured into two sections: the main section on the importance of a variety of outcomes to assess the effect of FMT on the microbiota, and a section inquiring about SOPs and guidelines.

Your input to both sections is required – the more information we have, the better we can reach a consensus on the minimum set of outcomes to measure when assessing the effect on the microbiome in FMT trials.

Please note that this consultation can be filled in by:

- individual experts, academics, physicians,
- Industry representatives,
- Regulatory bodies.

This DELPHI is run in two rounds (with a third round only if necessary) and your contribution (should you accept) to all rounds is required. With the results of this two-round DELPHI consensus project, we aim to inform the scientific community and the general public with comprehensive and consensual insights in the form of scientific publications and conference presentations.

Please be aware that FIVE different DELPHIs are underway within the overall Human Microbiome Action project. You may be involved in one or several questionnaires, according to your expertise and willingness to contribute to the project.

If you are interested in being part of this DELPHI, please follow this link:

[Link to the survey]

Username: %USERNAME%

Password: %PASSWORD%

We kindly ask you to provide your feedback on this questionnaire by (XX date). Filling out this survey will take less than 30 minutes.

Please be aware of the following:

- **For security reasons**, the password is updated every time a reminder email is sent. If you haven't accessed the platform yet, please use the password provided in the current email.
- **Each session expires after 1 hour of inactivity**. If you expect to take a break before the end of the session or leave your computer, **please validate your answers** first. You can then re-enter the survey to finalize it. Error messages informing you that you have not finished the questionnaire will appear (red boxes): you can go back to these unanswered questions at your convenience.

In case you need further information, or you face a technical issue, please contact:
alexander.jarde@cochrane.fr

We thank you for your support!

With kind regards,

Emmanuelle Maguin, on behalf of the Human Microbiome Action project.

Reminder email:

Subject: DELPHI Survey – Human Microbiome Action – Core outcomes in FMT

Dear colleague,

This is a friendly reminder that we are yet to receive your feedback on the following DELPHI survey: 'What is the minimum set of outcomes to measure when assessing the effect on the microbiome'.

This DELPHI survey is undertaken under the European program IHMCSA - Human Microbiome Action (<https://humanmicrobiomeaction.eu/>) and is due by (XX date).

We would appreciate your contribution by filling in the questionnaire below:

[Link to the survey]

Username: %USERNAME%

New Password: %PASSWORD%

Please be aware of the following:

- **For security reasons**, the password is updated every time a reminder email is sent. If you haven't accessed the platform yet, please use the password provided in the current email.
- **Each session expires after 1 hour of inactivity**. If you expect to take a break before the end of the session or leave your computer, **please validate your answers** first. You can then re-enter the survey to finalize it. Error messages informing you that you have not finished the questionnaire will appear (red boxes): you can go back to these unanswered questions at your convenience.

As previously described in our email, the outcome of this DELPHI will include a consensus statement reflecting expert opinions on the minimum set of outcomes to measure when assessing the effect on the microbiome in FMT trials.

Thank you for sharing your input through this survey,

Yours sincerely,

Emmanuelle Maguin, on behalf of the Human Microbiome Action project.